

BIO-SUSHY

Sustainable surface protection by glass-like hybrid and biomaterials coatings

Deliverable D.5.2

Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities (PDEC)

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Publishable Summary

This Deliverable D5.2 Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities (PDEC) updated version in month 6, is the first review PDEC for the BIO-SUSHY project initially included in the proposal and later as part of the Grant Agreement.

The Deliverable aims to present a comprehensive report on the tasks carried out during the initial 6-month period and present strategies for the Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation of the BIO-SUSHY project.

After highlighting the Objectives (Chapter 1) and Introduction (Chapter 2), Chapter 3 of the deliverable focuses on the partners' description and includes a summary of their role and their expectation for valuable mature results to be exploited at the end of the project. Chapter 4 refers to the Dissemination and Communication Plan to effectively share the project objectives, findings, and outcomes. The plan includes tactics and channels such as a project website, social platforms, newsletters, press releases, and events. The target audience comprises researchers, policymakers, industry professionals, and the general public. Key performance indicators and monitoring processes are in place to evaluate the success of the communication and dissemination activities. By implementing this plan, BIO-SUSHY aims to maximise the impact and engagement of its research within the relevant communities.

Next, Chapter 5 defines the Exploitation Strategy of the BIO-SUSHY innovative developments. It outlines the proposed exploitation schedule and knowledge management strategy towards the potential market entrance of the BIO-SUSHY innovations beyond the project lifetime. It shapes the upcoming identification of the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and frames the future business plan strategies for industrial applications: textiles, food trays and cosmetic glass packaging. These measures will be developed under revisions at months M24 and M48, incorporating market analysis, patent landscape, competition, and risk analysis.

The aim of the PDEC is to maximize the adoption of the project results among diverse audiences and interested parties through a fit-for-purpose and appropriate dissemination and exploitation strategy.

The PDEC, a continuous endeavour, is developed through the project implementation, with 3 important landmarks, following the initial plan included in the proposal and Grant Agreement:

- D5.2 PDEC updated, at Month 6.
- D5.3 PDEC mid-term, at Month 24.
- D5.4 PDEC final, at Month 48.

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Table of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CA	Consortium Agreement
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
GA	Grant Agreement
HEU	Horizon Europe
IP(R)	Intellectual Property (Rights)
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KET	Key Emerging Technologies
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M00	Project's month age
OA	Open Access
PDEC	Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities
PESTLE	Political, Economic, Social, Technical, Legal, Environmental
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl Substances
ROL	Results Ownership List
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable By Design
SWOT	Strength, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats
WP	Work package

1. Objective

The objective of this deliverable, the “Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities,” is to outline a comprehensive strategy to maximise the impact of the BIO-SUSHY project. This plan focuses not only on the successful dissemination and future commercial exploitation of project outcomes but also on integrating the developed coatings into standardisation and certification programs, leveraging computational tools, and ensuring social acceptance.

The primary objective of the PDEC is to provide the partners of the BIO-SUSHY project with clear guidelines on their communication and dissemination activities as well as route their exploitation intentions. Specifically, in terms of communication and dissemination, the PDEC will:

- Establish the main communication and dissemination goals and the target audiences.
- List the channels and tools used to reach the identified audiences.
- Determine and monitor the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the success of the implementation.

These guidelines include information about planned activities, their schedule, the responsible partners, the tools and dissemination channels available, and the planned actions to ensure that project results are used effectively and impactfully.

Regarding the exploitation of the results, the PDEC will:

- Outline the methodology to identify the project’s Key Exploitable Results.
- Identify the relevant users and activities for transferring the results, as well as manage intellectual property.
- Identify the framework conditions and other factors that may influence the future use of the project’s results.

The document is initially drafted by AXIA INNOVATION, the leader of WP5, with input from all partners, and Materia Nova and RESCOLL doing a thorough review. The PDEC, a continuous endeavour, is developed through the project implementation, with 3 important landmarks, following the initial plan included in the proposal and Grant Agreement:

- D5.2 PDEC updated, at Month 6.
- D5.3 PDEC mid-term, at Month 24.
- D5.4 PDEC final, at Month 48.

In this first version, a special focus is on the strategy outlined behind the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan.

2. Introduction

2.1. BIO-SUSHY Project

The rapid growth of the bio-based industrial sector has conveyed numerous technological advancements and increased the demand for high-performance coatings. However, the use of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) in traditional coatings has raised significant concerns due to their environmental and health hazards. PFAS persist in the environment for an unknown duration and can impact human health, depending on their composition.

Regarding their application in surface treatments and coatings, PFAS are widely used to provide water and oil resistance in various contexts, such as non-stick cookware surfaces, water-repellent and stain-resistant treatments for textiles, anti-soiling coatings on food-contact paper or cardboard packaging. Although there are alternative products available on the market that do not contain PFAS, they do not fully meet all the long-lasting repellence requirements (especially for oleophobic properties), which limits their widespread adoption, and only few of those are bio-based.

To address this pressing issue, the BIO-SUSHY project has been initiated with the goal of developing bio-based advanced coatings with hydrophobic and oleophobic properties that can effectively replace PFAS. Additionally, to further ensure the extensive adoption of bio-based advanced coatings by the industry, the BIO-SUSHY project targets the coatings design by the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) methodology, allowing to reach required industry performances and increased durability. Moreover, it will actively participate in the development of a roadmap for relevant standards and guidelines, carried out by UNE, as well as a certification programme.

In addition, to accelerate the research advancements and technology development processes, the BIO-SUSHY project comprises computational tools such as advanced modelling, simulation, and predictive methods. These tools will be used to optimise the properties, performance, and application processes and will significantly contribute to the optimisation of the coating design, testing, and validation phases, ensuring cost-effective and efficient product development.

Besides, the project incorporates a social acceptance strategy in WP1 carried out by ZSI (Deliverable D1.5) as part of the successful implementation of bio-based coatings. A specific strategy through public engagement activities will be developed among consumers, communities, and other relevant stakeholders, to foster understanding and acceptance of bio-based advanced coatings, in terms of willingness to pay and co-designing R&I strategies.

2.2. BIO-SUSHY PDEC

The Communication and Dissemination strategy is a crucial aspect of the BIO-SUSHY project, aiming to ensure that the project, its outcomes, and advancements reach the targeted audience of stakeholders and broad society. It includes a multi-layered approach, including targeted dissemination messages, and channels that effectively resonate with relevant industrial sectors, academic communities, regulatory bodies, and the general public.

Specific dissemination and communication tools have been developed to establish the basis for future implementation of communication and dissemination activities, such as the BIO-SUSHY website, social media accounts, blogs, and advertising materials. In addition, various dissemination materials and tools will be made, such as publications, scientific articles, brochures, videos, and newsletters, to highlight the benefits and applications of bio-based advanced coatings and other project developments. Participation in conferences, workshops, and trade fairs will be actively pursued to showcase the project's results, engage with key stakeholders, and foster knowledge exchange.

The Exploitation of the BIO-SUSHY project outcomes is essential to ensure the successful use of valuable results and future expected positive impact, especially the integration of bio-based advanced coatings into the market that will lead to the replacement of the PFAS coatings. The exploitation strategy, currently under development, identifies the BIO-SUSHY valuable assets and prioritises potential post-project commercialization opportunities. It includes individual exploitation interests related to the KERs identified by each partner as well as a joint strategy targeting the business plans of the novel bio-based coatings within the BIO-SUSHY validations, including textiles, food trays and glass cosmetic packaging.

3. BIO-SUSHY partners

The BIO-SUSHY consortium integrates a full range of partners, from Academia and Research Institutes to Industrial end users and diverse consultancies and public bodies.

3.1. Researchers and Academia

Research and technological centers play a vital role in the application of research outcomes. These centers aim to bridge the gap between academia and industry by conducting front-line research and developing innovative technologies. Their primary goal in the utilisation of results is to transform research findings into practical applications, products, or services that can be commercially feasible. By collaborating with industry partners and stakeholders, they strive to transfer knowledge, promote technology transfer, and facilitate the commercialization of intellectual property. Through strategic partnerships, licensing agreements, and spin-off ventures, research and technological centers seek to maximize the societal and economic impact of their research by translating it into tangible outcomes that benefit industries, markets, and society. These will be carefully considered during the project's implementation.

3.1.1. MATERIA NOVA

Materia Nova is the coordinating partner. Materia Nova is a R&D centre dedicated to the development of innovative materials and processes. Main tasks in the project will be the development of hydrophobic/oleophobic coatings using hybrid organic (bio-based)/inorganic sol-gel processes, performing life cycle assessment and life cycle costing as part of the SSbD strategy.

3.1.2. CNR

The Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR) is Italy's National Research Council, a public research organization that conducts scientific research across various fields.

CNR will contribute to BIO-SUSHY with expertise on multi-scale and data-driven high-performance simulations of organic and hybrid interfaces.

**Consiglio Nazionale
delle Ricerche**

3.1.3. IFTH

IFTH (Institut Français du Textile et de l'Habillement) stands for the French Institute of Textile and Apparel and is the French technical centre for the fashion, textile and clothing sectors that aims to

support innovation and to promote the textile and clothing industry in France and abroad.

IFTH will develop PFAS-free functional coatings using sol-gel chemistry and will be involved in supporting textile standardisation and certification programme.

3.1.4. ITENE

ITENE (The Packaging, Transport and Logistics Research and Development Institute) is a research and development centre specialized in the packaging, transport, and logistics industry.

ITENE will contribute to BIO-SUSHY in developing the SSBD strategies of the coatings.

3.1.5. UNIVLEEDS

The University of Leeds is a public research university in Leeds, UK.

The University of Leeds will screen the coatings developed and use the screening results to modify the coating design.

3.1.6. Wood K Plus

Wood K plus is a research organisation based in Austria specialising in wood and wood-related renewable resources in Europe. Core competencies are materials research and process technology along the complete value chain – from raw materials to finished products. Within BIO-SUSHY project Wood K plus is responsible for powder coatings formulation development based on bio-based thermoplastic matrices which will be developed and adopted for electrostatic spraying and scattering coating technologies being applied as water repellent and grease resistance coating on paper-based substrates for takeaway food packaging. The team Sustainable Innovation and Impact Analysis (SIIA) of Wood K plus will further contribute to Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) particularly focusing on Social Life Cycle Assessment (s-LCA) in close cooperation with Materia Nova.

3.1.7. ZSI

ZSI, or the Centre for Social Innovation, is an Austrian research institute that focusses on the social, economic, and ecological aspects of innovation.

ZSI will lead the work on the social acceptance dimension and provide a sociotechnical perspective on embedding the novel coating approaches in current practises.

3.2. Industrial and end users

The goal of industrial and end users in BIO-SUSHY is to validate and improve products, processes, or services, thus gaining a competitive edge in the market by adopting these relevant technologies, methodologies, or solutions that align with their specific needs. By incorporating these findings into their manufacturing operations, producers can improve the efficiency, quality, sustainability, and innovation of their products. The exploitation of research results allows industrial end users to remain at the forefront of their respective industries, drive technological advancements, and address market demands effectively. By actively engaging in the exploitation process, industrial end users can capitalize on the value created by research and contribute to their own growth and success. The BIO-SUSHY validations in cellulosic food packaging, glass cosmetic packaging and textiles, integrate:

3.2.1. Ecozema

Ecozema is an Italian company that specializes in sustainable household products.

Ecozema will define the requirements of the application on cellulosic materials for food packaging, participate in testing the laboratory-applied products, and apply the selected coatings at a pilot/industrial scale, which might include the development of the application parameters and checking compatibility with thermoforming.

3.2.2. RESCOLL

RESCOLL is a private technology service company, which belongs to APPLUS + Laboratories group, that offers industrial research solutions on coating and adhesives and testing of polymer materials for a wide range of industries.

RESCOLL will develop functional coatings using sol-gel chemistry and will run all the required physico-chemical analysis of the developed products. This coating development will be focused on textile application.

3.2.3. SIKEMIA

Sikemia is a French SME specialised in the tailor-made design, synthesis and scale-up of linkers, coupling agents and functional additives.

SIKEMIA will set up organic synthesis routes starting as much as possible from biobased molecules to obtain fluorine-free components, used by the formulators of BioSushy consortium as additives to provide water repellence, and improve curing rate or adhesion.

3.3. Service providers

This group includes the service providers in the consortium, these are the partners offering a wide range of valuable services designed to meet the needs of industries and businesses. Companies can benefit from access to professional expertise, technical support, and solutions to enhance their operational efficiency, productivity, and effectiveness. Service providers are committed to delivering high-quality services, utilising their industry knowledge, infrastructure, and specialised skills.

3.3.1. Acumenist

AcumenIST is a SME registered under the Belgian Law, that supports both the private and the public sector with timely technology-specific expertise that enables its clients to draw the maximum benefits from science- and technology-based innovations, whilst minimising and managing their potential risks.

AcumenIST, an affiliated organisation from MATERIA NOVA, aims at providing a secretariat to the BIO-SUSHY External Advisory Board, though providing the EAB and the Project team with a collaboration platform. Additionally, supports the representation of the BIO-SUSHY project (and dissemination of its results) to policy-informing and -making committees (e.g. OECD WNT (National Coordinators Test-Guidelines Programme), NanoSafety Cluster, and strengthening of representation to the standardisation community (i.e. IST, CEN, VAMAS).

3.3.2. AXIA

AXIA Innovation is a business consulting company that provides services for Innovation Management, Technology Transfer as well as Marketing tools for companies and organizations, helping them to speed up the market uptake of their novel outputs. The goal of consultancy services is to provide expert guidance, advice, and strategic support to partners in utilising research results for their specific needs and ambitions.

AXIA leads dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities of BIO-SUSHY to develop a strong plan for the uptake of results, technology transfer and business strategies. AXIA's specialized expertise will assist the partners to navigate challenges, mitigating risks, and optimising the exploitation process. Custom solutions will allow partners to make informed decisions, maximise the value of research results, and achieve their desired outcomes effectively.

3.3.3. ProtoQSAR

ProtoQSAR is a company based in Valencia (Spain) that develops and applies computational methods to evaluate the properties of chemicals, including their physicochemical, biological and (eco)toxicological effects; as well as works in the optimization of molecules over molecular modelling and other computational tools.

Computational developer services are focused on leveraging research outcomes such as cutting-edge technologies into practical solutions based on information technologies. Their primary goal is to develop and provide computational tools, platforms, or services that enable users to harness the benefits of research findings in their own projects or applications, thus, boosting the potential exploitation of results.

ProtoQSAR will contribute to the creation and population of the BIO-SUSHY datalake and, also, provide in-house QSAR models for properties prediction to bridge the gap between complex research algorithms and practical implementation.

3.3.4. 7P9

Seven Past Nine d.o.o., Slovenia (7P9-SI) and its affiliated partner Seven Past Nine GmbH, Germany (7P9-DE) are two SMEs specialising in data stewardship and knowledge management solutions for the life sciences industry. Due to their strong collaboration and common tasks in BIO-SUSHY, they will jointly be referred to 7P9 for the PDEC. They strive to make research outputs accessible, user-friendly, and scalable, empowering the project to utilise advanced modelling and simulation capabilities effectively.

7P9 will provide expertise in designing (meta)data formats, data warehouse development, and web application development complemented with targeted support of all data producing and using partners (experimental and computational) via their Data Shepherding service.

3.3.5. UNE

UNE (National Standardization Body of Spain) is a National Standards Body in Spain, responsible for the standardization and certification in the Spanish market. Standardization organisations work to develop consensus-based technical standards that ensure

interoperability, compatibility, and quality in products, processes, and services. These standards provide a common framework for industry players to follow, promoting harmonisation, innovation, and market growth.

UNE is responsible for advice, managing, and developing all activities related to standardisation. UNE also contributes to the successful exploitation of research results by providing clear guidelines, promoting trust, and fostering a conducive ecosystem for safeguarding innovation and technology transfer.

3.4. The BIO-SUSHY Value Chain

The BIO-SUSHY partners' alliance for the three novel bio-based coatings developments is shown in Figure 1 BIO-SUSHY project value chain. From modelling and computational tools, formulation of coatings and development of additives, scaling up, characterization and standardisation, and validation in end-use cases, including social acceptance, SSbD assessment, S-LCA and LCC and communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities.

Figure 1: BIO-SUSHY project value chain

4. Communication and Dissemination Plan

Communication and dissemination (C&D) play a fundamental role in every research project, as the knowledge of valuable scientific results produced within the project can reach and benefit identified target groups and society.

This becomes especially important when a project aims at replacing harmful chemicals present in almost every consumer product with an impact on the whole value chain, as shown in Figure 1.

After introducing some definitions, this chapter outlines the goals, responsibilities, target audiences, tactics and channels used, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and the tracking and monitoring of the C&D activities.

4.1. Definition of Communication and Dissemination and significance in Horizon Europe projects

Although closely related terms, communication and dissemination refer to distinct aspects for which it is essential to introduce their definitions initially.

Communication, compared to dissemination, is a broader term, and it involves the promotion of both the actions and the results of the project. On the other hand, dissemination is more specific and involves sharing the results with users.

As stated in the annotated grant agreement under Article 17 – Communication, Dissemination and Visibility (and Annex 5), it is obligatory to acknowledge EU funding support using the appropriate EU emblem and the funding disclaimer²: “Acknowledge EU funding in all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, as well as on all equipment, infrastructure and major results financed by EU.”

Furthermore, according to the consortium agreement, any planned publication shall be provided to the other partners at least 15 days prior to the publication. If there are objections to the intended publication, they must be raised within 30 calendar days after receiving the notice. Objections should be made in writing and addressed to both the Project Coordinator and the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination.

The EU acknowledgments and text to be displayed are the following:

² https://commission.europa.eu/funding-tenders/managing-your-project/communicating-and-raising-eu-visibility_en

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Figure 2: Horizontal and vertical EU emblem.

“Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement 101091464. Views and opinion expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

4.2. Communication and Dissemination responsibilities

Being AXIA Innovation the WP5 leader as well as leader in the Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation, and Clustering tasks, AXIA will be the main partner responsible for the tasks related to C&D analysis, strategic planning, management, and monitoring. AXIA is committed to providing the BIO-SUSHY consortium with their best expertise and tools to maximize the impact of the project as much as possible.

On the other hand, the BIO-SUSHY consortium is expected to contribute to C&D activities, especially at the planning and reporting level. Each partner is committed to the following:

- Participate actively in C&D activities and promote the BIO-SUSHY project and its outcomes.
- Facilitate access of BIO-SUSHY to open access journals, scientific research societies, and networks.
- Take advantage of any opportunities to publicly present the BIO-SUSHY project and its nonconfidential outcomes at scientific events, conferences, forums, festivals, and other similar events.
- Suggest media, scientific journals, and scientific events in their country suitable for promoting and disseminating the BIO-SUSHY project and its outcomes. They must also translate general press releases prepared by the WP5 Leader into their native language and distribute them to the media in their country.
- Identify a contact person within their organisation to periodically communicate with the C&D leader, which will facilitate the following:
 - Provide the necessary information before and after C&D activities by periodically (i.e., monthly) filling in the online spreadsheet to track activities.
 - Communicate with the WP5 Leader regarding any C&D issues.

4.3. Communication and Dissemination roadmap

The C&D can be planned in the following order:

1. Define the objectives (see 4.4)
2. Identify the target audience (see 4.5)
3. Pick the right tactics or channels (see 4.6)
4. Establish key performance indicators (KPIs) (see 4.9)
5. Continuously track, monitor, and adjust to meet KPIs effectively (see 4.10)

Overall, the C&D planning timeline can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Overview of the C&D plan within the project lifespan.

4.4. Communication and Dissemination goals

In the BIO-SUSHY project, the objectives of the C&D activities can be listed as follows:

- Increase the project’s visibility.
- Promote the project’s goals and results including technologies and methods.
- Explain in an easy and understandable language the project objectives and topic.
- Increase awareness of the effects of PFAS on the environment and human health.
- Contribute to lower PFAS-containing product consumption or PFAS production.
- Increase the acceptance of newly developed materials and/or coatings among customers & end-users.
- Increase transparency and build trust with potential and prospective customers & end-users.
- Promote how HEU funding helps research and innovation programme.
- Attract potential users.

4.5. Target audience

Target audiences are set in the GA. However, among communication and dissemination, the target audience might be different.

In fact, in communication, the ultimate goal is to increase the visibility of the project on a broader level. For dissemination, the audiences can be more specific and even prioritised according to the purpose of the dissemination measure.

Table 1 summarises the target audiences of BIO-SUSHY.

Table 1: Target audiences, messages, and tools.

Target audience and segmentation		Objective/Messages	Tools
Research organisations, Academia	Sustainability and coating R&I communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information and knowledge sharing about BIO-SUSHY scientific and technology development. Alignment of SSbD indicators and SSbD concepts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications in peer-reviewed journals. Posters and/or presentations at conferences and workshops
	Related initiatives and projects		
Policy-informing, Policy-making Committees and Safety Communities	Agency and certification bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote the use of PFAS-free products supported by certification. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation and presentation of results at events. Direct contact (sending/email project information to contact persons). Writing policy briefs and participating in white papers.
	Standardisation Technical Committees and Communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination of scientific and technical results. Relevant BIO-SUSHY standardisation and harmonisation activities. Alignment of SSbD indicators with current policies Communication of project results to the OECD TG committee and to the OECD SIA-Project. 	
	Regional and national organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing BIO-SUSHY outcomes with the EU nanomaterial modelling and characterization communities 	
	European and international councils, associations		
	NanoSafety Cluster, US-EU communities of research (CoRs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share BIO-SUSHY environmental, health, and 	

		CUSP cluster, in micro- and nanoplastics and human health	safety best practices and contribute to nanomaterial advance. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote BIO-SUSHY safe and human health results. 	events, invited stakeholders to BIO-SUSHY events.
Industry		Textile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inform and create interest in the project results. User/customer of the BIO-SUSHY platform & tool (models, SSbD decision tool) Provide training. Special use-case support. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events Sectorial publications E-newsletter
		Packaging		
		Coatings & Surfaces		
		Nanoplastics		
General public		Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generate visibility for BIO-SUSHY. Provide technology and market information. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Website Social media Press and broadcast
		EU citizens		
		Non-government organizations (NGOs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage and co-design social-acceptance strategies. Involve quadrupole helix actors. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> BIO-SUSHY media channels. Social engagement community activities.
		Civil society organizations (CSOs)		

4.6. Tactics and channels for Communication and Dissemination

To maximise the impact of the BIO-SUSHY project, it is fundamental to not rely only on a single or limited channel; instead, a diverse range of C&D channels should be employed. By utilising multiple channels, the visibility and impact of the project can be amplified. This multichannel approach aims to engage with various audiences effectively and involves (but is not limited to):

- The development of a project **website**.
- An active presence on relevant **social media** platforms to engage with stakeholders, share project updates and foster dialogue.
- The creation of **printable materials** for on-site distribution to provide an overview of the project's goals and activities.
- Creating a periodic **newsletter** to share project updates, highlights, upcoming events, etc.
- Run **webinars** to facilitate knowledge exchange and display the findings of the project to a targeted audience.
- The release of concise and compelling **press releases** to announce milestones, major project results and noteworthy events.
- Participation in fairs, conferences, and other **events** related to the scope of the project, providing opportunities for direct participation and dissemination.
- The publication of scientific and technical **papers** in reputable journals and conferences to contribute to the academic and research communities.

4.6.1. Website

The project website is available since M03 (March 2023) at the following address: www.bio-sushy.eu, it represents the main point of contact with external stakeholders to the BIO-SUSHY project.

As described in deliverable D5.1, it was developed with an easy-to-navigate concept, able to reach a broad audience as the main interface with potential stakeholders and the public worldwide.

The website is structured in several parts to give visitors an idea of the project, the team, the updates, the technologies and the methodology used or developed, and the contact information.

Furthermore, the website is also a useful tool for partners, as they can directly access the internal online platform and download any communication materials, such as brochures, etc., from the '[Dissemination Library](#)' tab (Figure 4).

BIO-SUSHY Dissemination Content

Figure 4: Screenshot of the "Dissemination Material" tab of the BIO-SUSHY website.

4.6.1.1. Blog articles

Within the project website, a section is dedicated to "[Blog Articles](#)" (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Screenshot of the Blog article section of the website.

The **blog articles** aim to promote the BIO-SUSHY project, its specific benefits, and results, and to make the scientific context more understandable. The targeted **audience** for the website and social media channels is in fact the general public.

The blog articles will be published **every four months** (for a total of ten articles), and the identified **content** is provisionally listed as follows:

1. Introduction of the BIO-SUSHY project: challenge, problem, solution

2. Market application
3. SSbD: What is it?
4. The social acceptance
5. Computational Tools
6. PFAS-free coatings
7. Hybrid Sol-Gel Coatings
8. Showcase of sample
9. Standardisation
10. Final closure

Nevertheless, as mentioned above, the plan is provisional and might be updated as the project progresses.

The **format** used for the blog articles will be around 500 words with attached visuals, either brief video or picture. The visuals will be developed according to the corporate identity of the project (see deliverable D5.1).

Aiming to attract stakeholders and inform the general public, the **language style** will be nontechnical, avoiding jargon and scientific terms. Besides, a conversational **tone of voice** will be established, and the second person (use of *you*) will be adopted to have a more direct impact on the readers and create a deeper connection with them.

4.6.2. Social platforms

As for the Blog Articles, in the social platforms, the tone of voice will be conversational and enthusiastic.

The BIO-SUSHY project is currently available on two main social media platforms used for industry professionals and news and updates:

- LinkedIn: @BIO-SUSHY (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/bio-sushy-project/>)
- Twitter: @BIO_SUSHY (https://twitter.com/BIO_SUSHY)

Posting frequency: weekly

Hashtags: #BIOSUSHY #BIOSUSHYProject #HorizonEU #HorizonEurope #SSbD #SustainableCoatings #coatings #Horizon #SafeandSustainablebyDesign #InnovativeCoatings #sustainability #foodpackaging #innovativecoatings #textile

Partners are encouraged to engage with the content posted by BIO-SUSHY, from following the pages to liking, commenting, and sharing content.

In addition, partners and funding agencies will be tagged in every posting activity to increase engagement and reach wider communities.

4.6.3. Newsletters

The newsletter is a further digital communication channel to reach and update the interested audience. In BIO-SUSHY, a semestral electronic newsletter will be distributed via LinkedIn with highlights of the project’s progress and achievements (news section), upcoming events and opportunities (events section), featured publications (publications section), success stories (stories section), and much more.

Similarly, inclusion in other partner-related newsletters will be targeted to reach further communities.

The first issue of the BIO-SUSHY newsletter (Figure 6) was already launched in M05 through the project’s LinkedIn account and can be found [here \(PDF version\)](#).

Figure 6: First BIO-SUSHY LinkedIn Newsletter.

4.6.4. Press releases

The purpose of the press releases is to attract public interest through various media platforms, including magazines, television, radio, and other channels used for media coverage. These press releases focus on significant project events such as the Kick-off meeting (KoM), project achievements, and consortium meetings. According to the GA, at least four press releases are planned, with one release scheduled for each year of the project.

The first press release (Figure 7) was launched on M03 right after the Kick-off meeting and workshop, and can be downloaded [here](#).

Figure 7: First BIO-SUSHY press release on Kick-off meeting and internal workshop.

4.6.5. Publications

BIO-SUSHY will follow open science and open data policies for the publication of its research results, as it is a mandatory requirement for HEU projects. However, partners may first need to comply with the obligation to protect results and then to disseminate in Open Access (OA) form.

The specific guidelines for the publication process are outlined in the HEU model grant agreement:

- Article 16: IPR – Background and Results – Access rights and rights of use
- Article 17: Communication, Dissemination and Visibility
- Annex 5 “Specific Rules”

The benefits of publishing research results following OA strategies come with several benefits for science itself, the economy, and society, as depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8: The benefits of Open Access (OA) to scientific peer-reviewed publications (source OpenAIRE.eu).

Partners, to make their research openly accessible right away, can do one of these two things:

- Put their publication in an online archive that allows OA.
- Publish in an OA journal.

In either case, they must also upload their publications to an online archive.

To rapidly check the OA journal policies, please visit: <https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>

An example of a trusted repository is the [Zenodo](#) platform, which is associated with [OpenAIRE](#). Such a platform is designed to facilitate the OA to scientific articles and data.

Another possibility of publishing in OA is Open Research Europe ([ORE](#)), a publishing platform for scientific research papers funded by Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020.

Furthermore, research data generated within the project must adhere to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) data principles. Thus, research data will need to be “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”.

4.6.6. Events

Attending and presenting at relevant scientific and/or industrial conferences, workshops, round tables, etc. related to the project’s fields (e.g., bio-based materials, coatings, food packaging, social acceptance, standardisation, textile) is crucial to share and disseminate the project’s results and impact. This can happen through presentations, posters, papers, or networking events. Table 2 provides a list of the attended events from the Consortium.

Table 2: List of attended events from the Consortium (period covered: January 1 - June 15, 2023).

Name	Place and Date	Event type	Partner
Genotoxic Impurities in Pharmaceutical Industry	Barcelona, Spain 26-27 January 2023	Conference	ProtoQSAR
Towards a sustainable future for coatings and the pain industry	Leuven, Belgium 09 March 2023	Technical workshop	Materia Nova
PARC FAIR Data and Tools webinar series	Online 09 March 2023	Webinar	7P9
European Coating Show	Nuremberg, Germany 28-30 March 2023	Conference, Fair	SIKEMIA
HEU Community Deep Dive "Social Innovation"	Online 11 April 2023	Webinar	ZSI
Example FIPs - WorldFAIR project: Chemistry & Nanomaterials	Online ?	Webinar?	7P9[1]
CHASE Expert Day	Linz, Austria 25-26 April 2023	Event	Wood K plus
SETAC Europe 33 rd Annual Meeting	Dublin, Ireland (Online) 30 April - 4 May 2023	Conference	ProtoQSAR
Nanosafety Training School	Venice, Italy 15-19 May 2023	Conference	7P9 UNIVLEEDS ITENE AIST
Exploitation and IPR Management. KER Identification	Online 24 May 2023	Internal session	AXIA All partners
nanoSAFE International Conference on Environment, Health and Safety issues related to Nanomaterials	Grenoble, France 5-9 June 2023	Conference	7P9 UNIVLEEDS

4.7. Clustering activities

Within WP.5, task T5.3 starting with M06, is allocated to synergies and clustering. The potential collaboration will be assessed with active EU-funded projects, EU policies and programmes and industry players and associations. According to Horizon Europe’s indications, the objective is to foster knowledge exchange between projects related to SSbD materials, repellent hybrid coatings, and thermoplastic powder.

Besides AXIA, key BIO-SUSHY partners to stimulate and promote clustering activities are Materia Nova, ZSI and 7P9, with involvement from all the partners.

Table 3 lists the sister projects under the same call for proposals of BIO-SUSHY (i.e. [HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-23](#)).

Table 3: BIO-SUSHY’s sister projects.

Acronym	Project ID	Title	Organisation
PROPLANE I	101091842	Enhanced Safe and Sustainable coatings for supporting the Planet	IDENER Research & Development Agrupacion De Interes Economico
TORNADO	101091944	New Routes of Safe and Sustainable by Design Water and Oil Repellent Bio-based Coatings	Fundacion Tecnalia Research & Innovation
ZeroF	101092164	Development of verified safe and sustainable PFAS-free coatings for food packaging and upholstery textile applications	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY

Additionally, BIO-SUSHY will seek potential synergies with other EU-funded projects targeting safe- and sustainable- by-design materials leveraging the extensive experience, in particular under CSA topic HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-08, *The InteRnational ecosystem for accelerating the transition to Safe-and-Sustainable-by-design materials, products and processes* ([IRISS project](#)). Similarly, BIO-SUSHY will also participate to the SSbD framework test [PARC](#) (Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals).

Moreover, BIO-SUSHY partners have identified, as included in the GA, other synergies with national and international R&I activities they are already involved in (Table 4).

Table 4: List of R&I activities related to the Consortium and the BIO-SUSHY project.

R&I activity	Project ID	Partner involved
SABYDOMA	H2020 - GA: 862296	UNIVLEED,

Approaching the Safety-by-Design with a technological platform coupling screening to production and/or release		RESCOLL
MOSTOPHOS		
Modelling stability of organic Phosphorescent light-emitting diodes. Multiscale modelling of devices based on organic materials	H2020 - 646259	CNR
SBd4Nano		
Development of safe and functional engineered nanomaterials (ENMs) and nano-enabled products (NEPs)	H2020 - 862195	ITENE
SUNSHINE		
Develops safe and sustainable-by-design strategies for multi-component nanomaterials, including those with high aspect ratio nanoparticles	H2020 - 952924	ITENE, CNR
EIROS		
Erosion and ice resistant composite for severe operating conditions	H2020 - 685842	SIK
POWDER EXTERIOR WOOD IRA SME transnational		
Development of a process for weather-resistant coating of wood and wood fiber composite materials	1723551	WOOD K PLUS
CHOPIN and STELLAR		
Coatings with hydrophobic and /or omniphobic properties against insect contamination on aircraft leading edges and smart eco-friendly anticontamination technologies for laminar wings	H2020 - 785484 H2020 - 864769	MANO
MATCHING		
Reduction of cooling water demand in the energy sector through innovative technological solutions, to be demonstrated in thermal and geothermal power plants	H2020 - GA686031	MANO
DEPERFLEX II		
Water repellent fluorine-free coatings	French National	IFTH
INN-PRESSME		
Open innovation ecosystem for sustainable Plant-based nano-enabled biomaterials deployment for packaging, transport and consumer goods	H2020 - 952972	UNE
NOFORMOL and AFTER		
Development of fluorinated-free textile finishing products	French National	RESCOLL, IFTH

EcoCosmePharm

Computational evaluation of the ecotoxicity of pharmaceutical and cosmetic materials: an approach towards a green and sustainable environment

H2020-MSCA-IF-SE

UNE

NanoQSAR

Structure activity relationship modelling of REACH-relevant endpoints to predict the toxicity of nanomaterials

H2020-MSCA-IF-SE - 896848

PROTOQSAR

GenoQSAR

Genotoxicity prediction by means of QSAR methods for regulatory purposes

H2020-MSCA-IF-SE - 101030422

PROTOQSAR

NanoCommons

Nanosafety knowledge infrastructure developing and implementing data curation, management and sharing concepts and link these with nanoinformatic services

H2020 - 731032

7P9

BLOOM

Boost European citizen's knowledge and awareness of the bioeconomy through open and informed dialogues. The activities supported the reduction of barriers towards bioeconomy and stimulated bioeconomy activities

H2020 - 773983

ZSI

BIONANOPOLYS

Open Innovation Test Bed for developing safe nano-enabled bio-based materials and polymer bionanocomposites for multifunctional and new advanced applications

H2020 - 953206

AXIA,
ITENE

MACRAMÉ

Advanced Characterisation Methodologies to assess and predict the Health and Environmental Risks of Advanced Materials

HEU - 101092686

AIST,
79P

4.8. Corporate image and communication tools

The corporate image and communication tools were submitted at M03 in deliverable D5.1. Its purpose was to explain the process of creating the visual identity for the BIO-SUSHY project. It emphasises the importance of establishing a strong and recognizable visual identity that people can associate with the project.

The deliverable is divided into two main sections: Corporate Image and Communication Tools.

In the Corporate Image section, the document outlines the visual identity elements of the project, including the logo, colour palette, and fonts. It provides guidelines for maintaining consistency in the

project's visual identity and explains the usage of Word and PowerPoint templates specific to the project. Various templates are listed, such as deliverable template, presentation template, meeting agenda, meeting minutes, participant list, and consent photography. Additionally, the document describes the project's communication material portfolio, which includes items like a leaflet, brochure, roll-up, poster, presentation pitch, lanyard, and folder. Below, some extracts of these materials can be seen (Figure 9, Figure 10, and Figure 11).

Figure 9: BIO-SUSHY leaflet.

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Figure 10: Extract of the brochure.

Figure 11: Extracts of the project's presentation pitch.

On the other hand, the Communication Tools section focuses on the project's website and social media channels. It offers guidelines for creating social media posts using the project's social media post templates. The document concludes by summarising the project's communication tools and their potential for promoting the project effectively.

To access all the related materials, please visit the developed material at the “Dissemination Library” tab of the project’s website at the following link: <https://www.bio-sushy.eu/dc-materials/>

For more detailed information, readers are referred to the public deliverable D5.1 submitted at M03.

4.9. Key performance indicators (KPI)

To enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of C&D actions, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are employed to track the progress of these activities. These metrics consist of specific milestones that are intended to be achieved by the project’s conclusion (at M48). They are regularly monitored and reported to comprehensively evaluate the C&D strategy and guarantee its achievements.

A detailed description of the KPIs utilized for managing the communication and dissemination activities in the BIO-SUSHY project can be found in paragraphs 4.9.1 and 4.9.2, respectively.

4.9.1. Communication activities

In Table 5, the KPIs status of communication activities are presented along with their description, the target audience and the outcome.

Table 5: KPIs status for Communication activities.

Communication Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Outcome	Status (31.05.2023)
Visual identity	Logo, templates, banner, etc.	All	Website, social media, print materials, newsletter	Visible in all tools and materials	Delivered
Website	Project website available	All		Visits: 3000 Downloads: 1000	Ongoing Visits: 764 Downloads: 50
Blog articles	Promoting BIO-SUSHY project in easy-to-understand language	All	Website, social media	Articles: 10 Views: 200	Ongoing Articles: 1 Views: 25
Leaflet, brochure, posters, roll-up, PPT presentations/pitch	To promote BIO-SUSHY project, results and benefits	All	Print materials, event	Leaflet/ brochure: 1000 copies distributed Poster: 2 Roll-up: 2 Project presentation in events: 4	Ongoing Leaflet/ brochure: 10 Poster: 1 Roll-up: 1 Project presentation: 1

Social media accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter)	To raise awareness and keep followers updated	All	Social media	Followers: 1000 Post: 120	Ongoing Followers: 258 Post: 39
E-newsletter and mailing lists	To connect with interested stakeholders. Cover events and exploit key results	Research communities, industry, institutions	Website, social media	E-newsletters: 8 Subscribers: 300	Ongoing E-newsletter: 1 Subscribers: 107
Press releases, general broadcasting	News or announcements about the project's results and impact for journalists, bloggers, or other media outlets.	All	Website, social media, press release	Press release: 4 (1/year)	Ongoing Press release: 1
Demo video (YouTube)	General diffusion and intro of the project and expected results	All	Video, website, social media	Video: 1 Views: 400	Ongoing Video: 0 Views: 0

4.9.2. Dissemination activities

In Table 6, the KPIs status of dissemination activities are presented along with their description, the target audience, the corresponding responsible partner, and the outcome.

Table 6: KPIs status for dissemination activities.

Dissemination Activity Name	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	Partner	Outcome	Status (31.05.2023)
Organisation of Webinars, Workshops	To share knowledge and attract industries	Industry		AXIA, All	Internal session: 1 Technical conference: 1	Ongoing Internal session: 1 Technical conference: 0
Exhibition stands	Display material, promote specific results and reach potential customers	Industry,	Event, Exhibition, Print materials	Technical partners, All	Events: 10 Print material distributed: 1000	Ongoing Events: X Print material distributed: X
Organisation participation in clustering activities	Develop synergies in SSbD strategies	Research communities, Industry, Institutions	Event	All	Events:4 Attendees: 100	Ongoing Events: X Attendees: 0
SSbD guidelines	Best practises for SSbD	Institutions	Other	ITENE	Downloads: 200	Ongoing Downloads: 0
Standardisation	Promoting modified or new standards based on BIO-SUSHY findings	Institutions, Research Communities, Industry	Other	UNE, All	Events participation: 3 Proposal contribution: 3	Ongoing Events participation: 0 Proposal contribution: 0

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Input to regulatory validation work	Input into new and ongoing regulatory validation work (i.e., OECD WNT, OECD SIA Project)	Policy makers, Institutions	Other	AIST, 7P9	Proposal contribution: 4	Ongoing Proposal contribution: 0
Round tables	Round tables with certification bodies, policy makers, and EC to align criteria	Policy makers, Institutions	Event	ITENE, MANO, IFTH	Event: 1 Attendees: 10 (min)	Ongoing Event: 0 Attendees: 0
Technical training	Seminar lessons and technical training for exchange of BIO-SUSHY developments	Research communities, industries	Event	MANO, ITENE, RESCOLL, WOODKPLUS	Session: 5 Attendees: 150	Ongoing Session: 0 Attendees: 0
Social acceptance	Build a stakeholder's group for co-design. Assess new material cost acceptance	General public	Event	ZSI	Workshop: 3 Members group: 20 Surveys: 4 (n=800)	Ongoing Workshop: 0 Members group: 0 Surveys: 0 (n=0)
Partner's websites	Publication of news and events	Research communities, Institutions, Industry	Website, social media	All	Post: 90 (6 posts/partner)	Post: 3

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Promotional video	Demo video to raise awareness and interest	General public, Industry, Research communities	Website, social media	AXIA, All	Video: 1 Views: 400	Ongoing Video: 0 Views: 0
Technical publication	Technical publications in the trade press and scientific journals	Industry, Research communities		Technical, Technological and Research partners	Publication: 10	Ongoing Publication: 0
Scientific publication	Scientific article and peer-review papers (according to OA practices)	Research communities, Industry, Institutions, General public		Technical, Technological and Research partners	Articles: 10	Ongoing Articles: 0
Scientific conferences and industrial fairs	Present project activities and results	Research communities, Industry, Institutions		Technical, Technological and Research partners	Participation: 15	Ongoing Participation: 0

4.10. Monitoring and timeline

The strategic planning of the C&D has started at the proposal stage. However, while communication of the project and results starts on day one and ends at the end of the project, the dissemination (and exploitation), which is related to the results, starts later and goes beyond the end of the project. In particular, dissemination will start when the first results are produced.

The monitoring serves a fundamental purpose in evaluating the achievement of the established KPIs and tracking the C&D activities planned and performed by all the partners.

In this chapter, the main tools for tracking the Consortium C&D activities, as well as the monitoring of the activities, are presented.

4.10.1. Internal scheduling

To effectively monitor the C&D activities of the BIO-SUSHY project, AXIA uses an internal Excel Gantt chart to manage and track project timelines and deadlines.

4.10.2. C&D form

As mentioned in Section 4.2, an online spreadsheet to collect the C&D activities will be made available to the partners to collect the C&D activities. It is composed of four fillable sheets:

- **BIO-SUSHY Publications:** Information details on the articles published within the BIO-SUSHY project (DOI, repository, journal, etc.).
- **BIO-SUSHY Dissemination Activ.:** Information of any dissemination activities where the BIO-SUSHY project's results were disseminated (event name, event location, event date, audience size, etc.).
- **BIO-SUSHY Communication Activ.:** Information on any communication activity carried out by the partners within the BIO-SUSHY project (mention on the project website, newsletter, etc.).
- **BIO-SUSHY Upcoming Events:** Events of interest to the project.

Moreover, a specific Google form (Figure 12) will be distributed among partners according to specific upcoming C&D actions (e.g., newsletter or press release) in order to facilitate the collection and handling of this information. The form is divided into the following parts:

1. Upcoming events
2. Attended events
3. Foreseen publications
4. Online communication

The questionnaire collects partners' updates and progresses to support their communication and dissemination through BIO-SUSHY's website, social media, and other C&D means such as Newsletters, Press releases, etc.

Figure 12: Extract of the Google Form.

4.10.3. Website analytics

BIO-SUSHY's was launched on March 28th, 2023, and the analytics presented in this section cover until May 30th, 2023 (Table 7).

Table 7: Total website views and top three main pages views of the project's website.

Total	Home	The Team	1st Press release
764	353	62	52

As reported in Table 8, it can be noticed that most of the users come from direct traffic, organic search (i.e., via search engine), and from the project's social networks.

Table 8: Traffic sources of the project's website (as of May 30, 2023).

Direct	Organic Search	Organic Social	Other
202	128	73	8

Although most users are located in Europe with the highest being Spain (31), France and Germany (23), the second main origin of visit is from the United States with 29 users (Figure 13).

Figure 13: World distribution of the number of users of the BIO-SUSHY website (as of May 30, 2023).

4.10.4. Social media metrics

Regularly collected data from SM metrics are utilized to monitor the performance of social media (SM) profiles in achieving established KPIs. These metrics involve extracting data and information from social media channels to assess the project's popularity. Key tools used for this purpose include LinkedIn Analytics and Twitter Analytics.

The data collected over a specific period, starting from the creation of the SM profiles on January 26th, 2023, until May 29th, 2023, encompass the following:

- Total number of followers
- Cumulative metrics of page views

- Outreach and post impressions
- Impressions and engagement

This section includes graphical representations derived from the analysed data, along with the significant insights generated through the analysis. It is important to note that the data collection period specified covers the timeframe mentioned above.

4.10.5. LinkedIn

In this section, the LinkedIn metric of the BIO-SUSHY's page is reported. In order to understand them clearly, a brief definition of the terminology used is provided.

The terms "Followers" and "Page views" are more immediate to understand as they are two metrics used to evaluate the total number of followers and of the project's page for the considered period (26 January – 29 May 2023), respectively. Instead "Impressions" represents the number of times people saw a specific post, and "Engagement", the number of times people engaged with the post (like, share, comment, click, etc.).

As it can be seen from Table 9, in four months from its creation the LinkedIn page reached 221 followers and collected more than 10 000 impressions. Around half of those impressions (namely, 4536) were reached during the month of February - when the page was officially launched and was used to promote the kick-off meeting held on February 8th, 2023 (Figure 14). Since then, the number of impressions and engagement per month kept steady at around 2000, and 200, respectively.

Table 9: Main metrics of the project's LinkedIn page (period covered: 26 January - 29 May 2023).

Followers	Impressions	Page views	Engagement
221	10 269	533	1 484

Figure 14: Total impressions and engagement trends for the project's LinkedIn page (period covered: 26 January - 29 May 2023).

4.10.6. Twitter

The covered period of the Twitter metrics presented in this section is from February 1st to May 31st, 2023.

Compared to LinkedIn, the Twitter page of the BIO-SUSHY project has a relatively small number of followers (34), but it has managed to generate a considerable number of impressions (5334) and engagement (545) (Table 10). This suggests that despite the limited number of followers, the project's content has been successful in reaching a broad audience and generating interaction from Twitter users.

Table 10: Main figures of the project's Twitter page (period covered: 1 February - 31 May 2023).

Followers	Impressions	Engagement
34	5 334	545

By having a closer look at the impressions and engagement over the last four months since the official launch, the Twitter page of the BIO-SUSHY project maintained a consistent presence with moderate impressions ranging from 1246 to 1392 and engagement ranging from 81 to 214 (Figure 15). This

suggests that the project has been able to foster some level of interaction throughout the period, possibly due to the consistent (weekly) posting strategy.

Figure 15: Total impressions and engagement trends of the Twitter page (period covered: 1 February - 31 May, 2023).

5. Exploitation Plan

The BIO-SUSHY Exploitation Plan explains the actions that partners will carry out to exploit the valuable results generated within the project, with the goal of maximising their positive effects on the society, economy and the environment.

The four pillars of exploitation to the achievement of long-term impact, as shown in Figure 16, are:

1. Identify and regularly update the Project Research and Innovation Results throughout the implementation and development.
2. Define the Exploitation Routes of the key results to better upgrade the impact in the market or industry in view of the partners’ strategic plan.
3. Develop a suitable knowledge management according to the type of results and the partners’ exploitation and business interest of the partners.
4. Enhance the Market Uptake of the results.

Figure 16: Exploitation pillars.

Further updates of the Exploitation Plan will follow at M24 under D5.3 PDEC mid-term and M48 under D5.4 PDEC final.

5.1. Exploitation Strategy

The BIO-SUSHY exploitation strategy targets maximising the valorisation of knowledge. As shown in Figure 17: BIO-SUSHY Exploitation Strategy, the aim is to efficiently use the results of the project by exploring scientific, economic, political, or social channels for exploitation.

It is focused on transforming research and innovation actions into tangible value and societal impact, not only addressing commercial interest, and targeting partners as well as other potential users outside the consortium.

Figure 17: Goals of BIO-SUSHY Exploitation Strategy.

To develop the exploitation plan, it is important that the partners understand the current context in which their results stand to properly assess their novelty and the potential value they bring. This will support making a proper exploitation analysis and exploitation route choice. Hence, AXIA will guide the partners in shaping the landscape through a comprehensive evaluation of the main external parameters that could influence the market uptake and upscaling of the project outcomes. These include market issues, regulatory framework, existing protection intentions of generated assets, industry requirements and competitors, and policy schemes, among others. In addition, internal factors that can accelerate or inhibit the exploitation will be also considered.

5.1.1. Exploitation Schedule

To carry out its exploitation strategy, BIO-SUSHY has established the following plan, Figure 18, showing the main activities during the implementation of the project. Three main periods have been scheduled and aligned with the PDEC deliverables: the first one M1-M6 (D5.2), M7-M24, to be included in D5.3, and M25-M48, D5.4 final PDEC.

	M1-M6	M7-M24	M25-M48
EXPLOITATION STRATEGY	Exploitation Routes IPRs	Update exploitation routes and Value proposition	Complete Business plans
IMPACT	Initiate KERs ID, Market analysis BIO-SUSHY SWOT & PESTLE	Update on Market analysis and KERs Categorization	Final ROL KERs Categorization update
VALIDATIONS	Industrial Applications Description	External Environment Patent analysis Risks & opportunities	Internal Environment IPRs Marketing

Figure 18: BIO-SUSHY Exploitation schedule planned.

5.1.2. Potential Exploitation Routes

Exploitation Route is the way the novel results of the project will be used in the future after the project ends.

Exploitation routes are linked to a strategic business decision and there are some important elements the partners should contemplate when assessing and evaluating what is the most suitable exploitation route for their results.

In general, it starts by considering whether the exploitation will be commercial or not, and what is the partner’s interest in commercialisation, if possible. Besides, some types of results have a pre-defined exploitation route. For example, a standard protocol will presumably feed into the Policy Recommendation category, as this result does not have a commercial implication. Whether the result needs further research and development or is in a prototype or validation stage, will also delineate the best exploitation route.

It is crucial for the partners to understand the goal of exploitation and how this will be achieved. Thus, AXIA organised an Exploitation and IPR internal workshop, on the 24th of May 2023 (Figure 19), to explain this to partners, assisting with their exploitation obligation and expected intentions. Chapter 5.2.2 of this deliverable includes further details of the workshop.

The workshop was followed by a KER identification template distributed among the partners that included some questions about the expected results and their exploitation routes and protection intentions. This will be further developed within the next implementation phase.

Figure 19: Presentation of the Exploitation and IPR - KER Identification internal workshop.

5.1.3. Knowledge Management

Knowledge Management refers to the coordination and organisation of the key assets and results generated within the project, their generators and owners, the way they will be exploited, IPR-protected, and who will be setting up rules and procedures. It also includes the background generated, before the project started, brought by the partners to implement the project’s actions, as included in the Consortium Agreement. The progress of the project and the next versions of this PDEC will include further considerations and updates on Knowledge Management and IPR.

BIO-SUSHY knowledge management strategy, planned parallel to the exploitation strategy, includes phases during and after the project, as indicated in Figure 20.

Figure 20: BIO-SUSHY Knowledge Management Strategy.

Important Knowledge Management and IPR concepts were explained, in the Exploitation and IPR internal workshop organised by AXIA on the 24th of May 2023, such as why it is important to protect,

if it is needed, and how an asset can be protected. Refer to Chapter 5.2.2. of this deliverable for further details.

The workshop was followed with a KER identification template distributed among the partners that included some questions about the expected results and their exploitation routes and protection intentions. This will be further developed within the next implementation phase.

5.2. Support to Partners

AXIA is supporting BIO-SUSHY partners in driving effective exploitation strategies and impactful outcomes. It is essential for the success of BIO-SUSHY to effectively leverage opportunities and maximise the potential of our joint efforts.

In this section, we highlight our dedicated support undertaken so far and designed to empower and enable our partners to excel in exploitation actions. We provide comprehensive resources, guidance, and materials to facilitate knowledge sharing, innovation, and real application. By fostering a culture of collaboration and assistance, we strive to provide BIO-SUSHY partners with the necessary tools to exploit emerging trends, seize market opportunities, and achieve a sustainable and meaningful impact.

5.2.1. Impact singularity in Horizon Europe – Internal Workshop

As part of the joint WP1-WP5 activity, led by Materia Nova in WP1, a *Coating Properties Alignment Workshop* was held physically at Materia Nova premises, on the 9th of February 2023, the following day of the BIO-SUSHY KoM Figure 21. The goal was to discuss coating properties' alignment with the needs of end-users (based on the identified case studies).

Figure 21: Impact Singularity in Horizon Europe Workshop.

AXIA, as leader of WP5 – ‘Maximising the Impact’, presented the ‘Impact Singularity of Horizon Europe’, the first session of the workshop. Focusing on the Project’s Pathways Towards Impact and its importance within the Horizons Europe framework, as described from the project to the destination level within the work programme. The spotlight was on introducing the partners to the innovations of the programme in the DEC rules and obligations for the beneficiaries.

Further explanation is included in Chapter 5.3 BIO-SUSHY Impact of this deliverable and in Deliverable D1.1 BIO-SUSHY R&I strategy, project scope description, specifications, and development planning report, submitted by Materia Nova at M3 (March 2023) of the project.

5.2.2. Exploitation and IPR Internal Workshop – KERs identification

To develop a realistic and successful BIO-SUSHY PDEC, AXIA provides support to the partners through diverse techniques advancing to their business interest and needs.

To harmonise the partners’ foundation and common understanding of Exploitation and Knowledge Management, AXIA organised the Exploitation and IPR workshop targeting the “Identification of Results”. The workshop included two Parts, **Part I theoretical**, to explain exploitation terms and definitions as well as knowledge management and IPR, and **Part II a practical exercise**, to learn how to identify potential Key Valuable/Exploitable Results. The second part included an explanation of the template as well to be distributed among the partners after the workshop.

The template will gather updates of the partners’ expected results. This will be followed, when required, by individual interviews, meetings and calls with partners to assist in the completion of the template towards the initial list of the Key Valuable Results.

5.2.2.1. Workshop data

- EVENT: Exploitation and IPR Workshop - Identification of Key Exploitable Results - KERs
- DATE: Wednesday, May 24, 2023, · Time 3:00 pm – 4:30 pm CEST
- ONLINE PLATFORM: Zoom (Internal BIO-SUSHY platform)
- PARTNER ORGANISING: AXIA Innovation
- 22 participants representing 13 partners attended the workshop.

5.2.2.2. Workshop programme

The agenda of the workshop, shown in Figure 22 included Exploitation, Knowledge Management and a practical session to support the identification of Key Exploitable Results.

BIO-SUSHY Exploitation and IPR management workshop

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 1. PDEC – Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication activities**
- 2. BIO-SUSHY Exploitation Strategy**
- 3. BIO-SUSHY Knowledge Management Strategy, including IPR**
- 4. Practicum - Identification of BIO-SUSHY KERs (Key Valuable Results)**

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Figure 22: Agenda of the Exploitation and IPR - KER Identification workshop.

The “Practicum” part, was an applied exercise for the attendees, aiming to identify potentially valuable results. AXIA presented the preliminary list of expected results based on the proposal and GA. Following, AXIA highlighted some recommendations to avoid common mistakes in the identification of exploitable results.

The presentations were given by Mrs Raquel Moreno, Project Manager and Innovation Consultant at AXIA Innovation, responsible for the BIO-SUSHY exploitation strategy, supported by her colleague Mr Michele Ponzelli, Project Manager responsible for Communication and Dissemination strategies (Figure 23).

BIO-SUSHY Exploitation and IPR management workshop

WHY? Do I have to care about exploitation and results?

Beneficiaries have obligation:

- TO DISSEMINATE
- TO EXPLOIT
- TO PROTECT

Maximising impact:

The focus of the Horizon Europe programme on activities which demonstrate and maximise the scientific, societal and economic impact of R&I funding → valorisation of (research) results

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Figure 23: Screenshot of the Exploitation Workshop.

To increase the partners' engagement, we used the sli.do© platform to make a dynamic session. AXIA created an interactive poll with the question "Which of these results are/could be a KER?" including 12 possible answers (multiple choice). The same question with the possible answers was presented at the beginning of the *Practicum* session and at the end, after explaining the specifics of the identification of KERs. The exercise included a final assessment of the comparison of both answers to this question and an explanation of the possible exploitation routes for each of these results.

The session ended with a discussion of the questions of the participants and an update of the partners on the next steps toward the final identification of KERs within the BIO-SUSHY project.

The partners highly rated the exploitation workshop, emphasizing that the session significantly enhanced their understanding and clarification of the exploitation strategy and the Key Exploitation Results (KERs).

5.3. BIO-SUSHY Impact

"The EU gears up to becoming a climate-neutral, circular and competitive economy by 2050". This is the European Commission's long-term strategy that leads the research and innovation BIO-SUSHY proposal.

BIO-SUSHY partners have considered the potential Impact of the project since the proposal stage. Following the Kick-Off Meeting, on the second day, the partners gathered in a workshop to discuss the alignment of the development of the three coating characterisation properties. The workshop started with a presentation focused on the Singularity of Impact, where AXIA explained the novelties of Horizon Europe regarding dissemination, communication and exploitation and the obligations and rights of the beneficiaries to exploit, disseminate and protect. It included specificities on the project's expected outcomes and impact to meet the call and destination targets and how the partners should approach the valorisation of results to maximise their impact.

The BIO-SUSHY project will develop innovative coating solutions that meet the EU's chemical strategy for sustainability and its ambition of a toxic-free environment.

The project aims to develop new bio-friendly ways to obtain durable water- and oil-repellent coatings that will be validated in three target markets: textiles, food packaging, and packaging for cosmetic applications. The project also targets to decrease environmental impact by 25% through the use of R&I coating development, computational modelling for performance, toxicity assessment, and SSbD methodology.

Additionally, the project will also contribute to the development of new standards to facilitate market acceptance and will aim to optimise the output through a programme of data harmonisation and management. Figure 24 shows the summary of **BIO-SUSHY outcomes** targeted by BIO-SUSHY partners as contained in the Topic Call: *Resilience, Green and Sustainable Materials*. A detailed explanation of each outcome follows in the following paragraphs.

Expected Outcomes

Figure 24: Topic Call expected outcomes.

BIO-SUSHY data-driven design to support SSbD concepts.

The BIO-SUSHY project aims to develop advanced coatings using computational tools, predictive models, and data-driven simulations.

It will use data from similar coatings to predict directions for further development and improvement of the materials and will use data-mining scripts to retrieve all available data from existing coatings.

The project will also use a data infrastructure that follows open science and FAIR principles to ensure harmonised sharing of the data in the project and allow public sharing at the earliest possible time.

Three novel organic or hybrid coating materials with hydrophobic & oleophobic properties.

The BIO-SUSHY project aims to develop eco-friendly organic/hybrid coating materials that are water and oil repellent.

These materials will be alternatives to PFAS based coatings and will be designed to be compatible with several substrates and end-user requirements. They will also be developed using SSbD concepts and modelling and will use life cycle assessment tools and toxicology studies as eco-design tools. The project aims to reduce the environmental impact by 25% and the production cost by less than 20%.

The developed materials will be validated in pre-industrial environments, and it is anticipated that the first coated materials will reach the market about two years after the end of the project.

Development of Safe- and Sustainable-by-design (SSbD) criteria.

The project uses a multidisciplinary approach to integrate sustainability strategies and eco-design principles into the organic and hybrid coating formulations to ensure safety concerns and sustainability criteria are addressed in the early stages of the innovation process.

The safety of the coatings will be ensured by minimising toxicity and environmental and human impact. At the same time, sustainability will be addressed by reducing environmental impact criteria such as climate change, resource use, and biodiversity loss towards a circular strategy. The development of the novel coatings will implement the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). The aim is to identify several alternatives leading to the best sustainability performances for the same functionality. The coatings will also comply with regulations and certifications related to the target applications.

The full SSbD assessment framework includes: Step 1 – Hazard assessment of the intrinsic properties of the chemicals on human health, environment and physical hazards; Step 2 – Human health and safety aspects of production and processing, to assess whether the production and processing of the chemical or material poses any risk to human health, in line with, or beyond, EU Occupational Health and Safety directives; Step 3 – Human health and environmental aspects in the final application, assesses exposure to the chemical or material and the associated risks in its final use to human health or the environment; Step 4 – Environmental sustainability assessment, the End of Life of the chemical/material are considered by means of an LCA, supported by LCC and S-LCA.

Enhance social acceptance of novel materials.

BIO-SUSHY project aims to enhance the social acceptance of the newly developed materials by compiling evidence-based data on consumer attitudes towards and willingness to pay for products that are less harmful to the environment and sustainable. A detailed analysis of the evidence gathered will allow to identify the level of acceptance of the novel materials.

Certification programme.

BIO-SUSHY is developing a certification programme throughout the value chain.

The programme will ensure conformity to legal norms and technical standards and compliance with final consumer requirements and international and regional directives. The certification programme will include a series of evaluation tests and a list of components to be avoided in the coating material composition and will comply with REACH regulations³ and certification bodies of the end-use cases targeted by BIO-SUSHY. This will be performed in order to safeguard the technical aspects that are of particular relevance while satisfying obligations such as safety and toxicity.

³ <https://echa.europa.eu/regulations/reach/legislation>

Process and method Standardization.

The BIO-SUSHY project will integrate existing standards and will be linked with ongoing standardization work in different areas like plastics, packaging, bio-based products and textiles.

This integration will support the exploitation of the project and its results, getting feedback from the stakeholders organised in standardisation and contributing to the development of new standards.

A roadmap will be prepared to provide for complete standardisation of the BIO-SUSHY results regarding PFAS-free materials and coatings, starting from the obtained standardisation results during the project and explaining the further activities needed. UNE will lead these activities supported by IFTH on textile applications.

Looking at the bigger picture, the Programme Destination in Cluster 4 *Increased Autonomy in Key Strategic Value Chains for Resilient Industry* has identified the expected impact, Figure 24. Proposals and projects should address some of these within their generated knowledge.

It is still too early to define the **potential impacts** that the BIO-SUSHY results are targeting. Nevertheless, preliminary expectations were included within the proposal, pointing out some of the anticipated impacts among the list included in the destination programme to support “industrial leadership and increased autonomy in key strategic value chains with the security of supply in raw materials” as outlined in Figure 25.

Figure 25: Cluster and destination expected impact.

Advanced Materials.

BIO-SUSHY aims to boost research, development, and innovation in the EU by developing new coatings for controlled wettability properties without PFAS on a laboratory and pre-industrial scale.

The modifiable character of the coating materials will make it possible to quickly adapt them to an extended area of substrates and end-uses. BIO-SUSHY will provide new material concepts that will improve the recyclability of the coating materials by the replacement of fluorine-based components.

The project also aims to provide data from physical modelling and experimental work as input for QSAR data-driven modelling tools that will be available for large-scale research and development in material science.

Circular value chains.

The BIO-SUSHY project aims to demonstrate the effectiveness and performance of alternative solutions with limited impact on production costs and strong positive effect on the environment and human health.

The project expects to contribute to the global reduction in the amount of PFAS in the environment and the consequent positive impact on human health and the environment.

Preparedness of businesses, SMEs, and start-ups.

The BIO-SUSHY project consortium aims to provide business opportunities for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by developing new products.

Five of the 14 partners in the consortium are SMEs, who will enrich their service portfolio with new business opportunities through the project enhancing their competitiveness: ProtoQSAR, AXIA, SIKEMIA, 7P9 and Ecozema. Besides, both affiliated parties, as described in Section 3 are also an SME.

5.3.1. BIO-SUSHY PESTLE

PESTLE analyses assess a market environment from the standpoint of a particular proposition or a business. The acronym stands for Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental factors that influence the organisation, in our case, the BIO-SUSHY project. As the project exerts no control over them, they are also called external environment.

The PESTLE analysis supports gathering landscape insight for potential strategic business development, including possible opportunities and threats towards market positioning. It is complementary and, in some cases, parallel to the SWOT analysis, which is included in the next section.

The BIO-SUSHY PESTLE analysis in Figure 26 shows the high potential of the project to get closer to the market.

Political and Legal⁴ aspects such as the European Green Deal⁵, Strategy for Financing the Transition to a Sustainable Economy⁶ and Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability⁷ lever the new developments and solutions offered by BIO-SUSHY partners. Other international initiatives include the United Nations, which has recently released the report “Turning off the Tap: How the world can end plastic

⁴ https://hadea.ec.europa.eu/news/safe-and-sustainable-design-chemicals-and-materials-commission-recommendation-and-hadeas-projects-2022-12-08_en

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2019%3A640%3AFIN>

⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2021:390:FIN>

⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2020%3A667%3AFIN>

pollution and create a circular economy⁸, to suggest some mechanisms for a systems change to address the causes of plastic pollution, towards circularity or the European Environment Agency-EEY, contributing with assessments, briefings, reports and open materials on circular strategies, chemicals or waste reduction among others⁹.

Figure 26: BIO-SUSHY PESTLE analysis.

Economic, environmental, and social elements are also assisting in the environment for the bio-based coatings, creating new employment, and making a better environment safer for human beings. The SSbD concept included in the project implementation plan together with the social acceptance strategy are key factors in the socially assertive assessment. Technology plays a dual role, with factors that could influence positively and negatively the project's success.

A deeper PESTLE analysis targeting the specific market opportunities of the novel solutions applications will be developed during the project implementation and included in future PDEC deliverables.

5.3.2. BIO-SUSHY SWOT

The BIO-SUSHY SWOT analysis, Figure 27, aims to measure the business potential of BIO-SUSHY as a whole, understanding the customers, capabilities and solutions of the BIO-SUSHY project, from a qualitative perspective.

⁸ <https://www.unep.org/resources/turning-off-tap-end-plastic-pollution-create-circular-economy>

⁹ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en>

Figure 27: BIO-SUSHY SWOT analysis.

The main Strengths of the consortium and its Weaknesses (internal attributes) are evaluated with its Opportunities and Threats (external factors). The strengths and opportunities give a vision of the attributes that help achieve the objectives of BIO-SUSHY. On the other side, the Weaknesses and Threats summarise the constraints that the partners will have to face to achieve the goals.

The partners' forces are the validation of the development of three bio-based coating materials with high functionalities, hydrophobic/oleophobic and anti-adhesion, reinforced by SSbD methodologies, the provision of social acceptance and computational tools, a standardisation roadmap, and a certification programme for the novel materials, to build up a strong reliable and consistent scheme. This is supported by the high market demand for sustainable and safer coating materials due to the European and International approach to circular value chains and the restrictions of the PFAS substances, the European initiative for more than 10,000 PFAS restrictions by the European Chemicals Agency-ECHA¹⁰.

The BIO-SUSHY consortium is prone to face a lack of price competitiveness in the market, funding, and financial support to reach industrial manufacturing, compliance with the product requirements by the end-users, and legal, regulatory and IPR management burdens. These factors will be deeply analysed as part of the BIO-SUSHY exploitation plan in order to find the routes to reduce and minimise their constraints, along with the implementation of the project, as part of the project technical validations in the textiles, food packaging and glass cosmetic packaging.

¹⁰ <https://echa.europa.eu/-/echa-publishes-PFAS-restriction-proposal>

5.3.3. BIO-SUSHY Market Analysis

Bio-based Coatings.

The growing consciousness and demand for environmentally responsible products are expected to drive the growth of the bio-based coatings market. Studies have shown that consumer preferences for sustainable brands and willingness to pay more for “green” products have drastically increased, propelling the growth of the bio-based coatings market, which is projected to grow from €6.84 billion in 2022 to €8.09 billion in 2023, with a CAGR of 18.3%¹¹. Despite the Russia-Ukraine war has disrupted global economic recovery, leading to inflation and supply chain disruptions, the bio-based coatings market is forecast to reach **€ 14.17 billion in 2027**¹¹, growing at a CAGR of 15.0%.

Hydrophobic, Superhydrophobic, Oleophobic and Omniphobic Coatings.

Regarding the Hydrophobic, Superhydrophobic, Oleophobic and Omniphobic Coatings, the market is large and growing, extended over the last decade in sectors such as packaging, textiles, plastics, aerospace and especially electronics (for waterproofing). The Global superhydrophobic coatings Market size is expected to reach **€ 110.82 million by 2030**¹², growing a CAGR of 25,2% from € 18,31 million in 2022. The same report highlights that there is a high trend in developing bio-based coatings with hydrophobic and oleophobic properties, and there are already some novel materials in the market, although the properties they offer can be enhanced, with the product requirements and advanced customisation the centre of the growth, orientated on end-user.

Superhydrophobic coatings are primarily used in the textile and footwear industries, offering strain resistance and water repellence, and are now being utilised in self-cleaning textiles. This reduces the need for washing, saving water and energy while increasing durability. The footwear industry also benefits from superhydrophobic coatings, keeping shoes dry and clean. The market is driven by these factors and the demand for quality footwear. The superhydrophobic coating industry will observe profitable business opportunities due to the significant increase in awareness and the emergence of various research and development actions.

Sol-gel Coatings.

Additionally, the sol-gel coatings market is estimated to grow at a CAGR of 11.69% between 2022 and 2027¹³, growing € 3.372 million, with a **global forecasted market of over € 4 billion by 2033**¹⁴. The market evolution depends on several aspects, including growing demand from the automotive and

¹¹ <https://www.thebusinessresearchcompany.com/report/bio-based-coatings-global-market-report>

¹² <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5662801/superhydrophobic-coatings-market-share-size#rela1-5778243>

¹³ <https://www.technavio.com/report/sol-gel-coatings-market-industry-analysis>

¹⁴ <https://www.factmr.com/report/sol-gel-coatings-market>

aerospace industries, these being the drivers for market growth: rising requests from building and construction applications, and improved performance properties and advanced characteristics. One of BIO-SUSHY's main applications of sol-gel coating is for textile garments. In addition, a validation of sol-gel coatings on glass packaging for cosmetics will be performed. Along with the project implementation, cookware and kitchen appliances application for the sol-gel coatings could be considered.

The key drivers of the non-stick sol-gel coatings market are the increasing demand from the automotive and aerospace industries and the need for eco-friendly coatings. Although it was impacted by the COVID pandemic with a collapse in prices and demand, the forecast expects growth of over 5% CAGR in 2027¹⁵.

Powder Coatings.

The global Powder Coatings Market is expected to grow at more than 4.2% CAGR from 2020 to 2029. It is expected to reach above **€19.43 billion by 2029** from €11.74 billion in 2020¹⁶. BIO-SUSHY food tray validation is framed in this market, where the main key drivers influencing powder coatings industry expansion are:

- recycling property of powder coatings to propel market growth prospects.
- increasing demand for environmentally friendly coatings to fuel the market growth.
- environmental challenges and local regulations to hamper the market growth.

5.3.4. Key Valuable Results

The exploitation strategy starts with the identification and definition of the most valuable results, also named Key Exploitable Results (KERs), of BIO-SUSHY developments.

These KERs refer to the outcomes produced throughout the project potentially to be used by the partners or other stakeholders outside the consortium, and which may have an impact by creating value for the economy, society, or the environment.

The project's expected results can take the form of inventions, prototypes, and services with high industrial and commercial potential, or they can consist of components like knowledge, technology, processes, and networks that require additional research or innovation development.

BIO-SUSHY partners have identified, individually or jointly, the expected results of their research activities as included in the grant agreement.

This will be updated within the first phase of the Exploitation Strategy, followed by the definition and characterization of the primary outcomes, where the more feasible to be exploited beyond the project life due to their economic, technical or research impact will be selected.

¹⁵ <https://www.mordorintelligence.com/industry-reports/non-stick-coatings-market>

¹⁶ <https://exactitudeconsultancy.com/reports/2775/powder-coatings-market/#segment-analysis>

To support the identification of expected results and identification of KERs list, AXIA organised the first Exploitation and IPR workshop on the 24th of May 2023, as detailed in Chapter 5.5.2. of this deliverable, focusing on the identification of valuable results.

After the workshop, AXIA distributed a questionnaire among the partners with specific questions about the potential exploitation routes and protection expectations as well as potential target groups and partners' involvement in each of the identified results, which are classified by the following types:

- Product: items for sale
- Process: ways to make or do
- Equipment: uses a process to make a product
- Knowledge and IP: valuation of "how to"
- Service: offer of products, processes, equipment, or knowledge
- Software, model: codes, algorithms
- Standard or contribution to policy: developing recommendations or implementing and developing technical protocols.
- Other: tools, platforms, databases

Further analysis will be needed to refine the input gathered and finalise the preliminary list of BIO-SUSHY KERs. The KERs list will be updated throughout the project's implementation, and it will feed the "Result Ownership List," to be delivered at the end of the project.

5.4. BIO-SUSHY validations

In the following PDEC versions, the BIO-SUSHY Exploitation Plan will target the specific business plans for the three validations included in the project: textile, food trays packaging and cosmetic glass packaging, targeting the potential commercial exploitation of the BIO-SUSHY coatings.

Sikemia's role is the development of the components of the bio-based coatings: additives, adhesion, curing and hydrophobicity.

Rescoll will develop new formulations for the hydrophobic hybrid sol-gel coating and IFTH will support the application and validation in the textile industry.

WoodK+ is expected to develop the bio-based powder coating formulations being applied onto paper substrates suitable for hot forming processes targeting the food tray as an end product. The powder coating formulation development as well as validation of the food trays will be done in close cooperation with an end user ECOZEMA.

Materia Nova will develop hybrid hydrophobic and oleophobic sol-gel coating formulations for cosmetic glass packaging, including its application and validation.

The future exploitation plan will include a patent analysis, aiming to gain a broad understanding of the current patent landscape within the three novel SSbD bio-based coatings. This involves conducting a preliminary search and analysis of patents that supports partners in:

- Identifying existing patents: to understand what technologies, innovations, or inventions have already been patented by others.
- Assessing novelty and potential patentability: to determine if a proposed invention is novel and potentially patentable.
- Identifying technology trends: emerging technologies, trends, and areas of innovation, identifying potential collaboration opportunities, or exploring untapped areas of innovation.
- Identifying potential infringement risks: this helps partners make informed decisions regarding developing and commercialising their innovations.
- Informing strategic decision-making: determining the scope of a proposed invention, identifying potential licensing opportunities, or deciding whether to proceed with a patent application and assessing the commercial viability and competitive landscape related to their outcome.

The preliminary discussions on the three BIO-SUSHY applications and coatings development properties included in Deliverable D1.1 *BIO-SUSHY R&I strategy, project scope description, specifications and development planning report*, submitted by Materia Nova at M3 (March 2023) of the project, will pave the grounds for setting up the future Business Plans.

6. Conclusions

The “Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation including Communication Activities” plays a vital role in maximising the impact of the BIO-SUSHY project.

By implementing a comprehensive approach encompassing strategic communication, dissemination and exploitation, BIO-SUSHY aims to ensure the effective development and adoption of bio-based advanced SSbD coatings as a sustainable alternative to PFAS containing benchmarks.

The Dissemination and Communication tools have been developed within the project’s first months to enhance and support the proper promotion of BIO-SUSHY. Numerous actions have been outlined by all the partners in order to diffuse the project idea, its results and the expected outcomes and impacts through its lifetime and beyond. Through strategic collaborations, knowledge sharing, and targeted dissemination, the project strives to create a positive and lasting impact on the coatings industry, the environment, and human health, the aim of the exploitation strategy.

The BIO-SUSHY project will collaborate with regulatory authorities, industry associations, industry manufacturers from textile, food and cosmetics, as well as other potentially interested industries, and standardisation bodies to align the developed coatings with existing norms and regulations, policies, and industry demands. This integration will enhance the marketability and credibility of the bio-based coatings developed following the SSbD European framework, enabling smooth and seamless adoption by industry players.

The Exploitation Plan, together with the Dissemination Plan, will target both commercial and non-commercial interests, as BIO-SUSHY aims to establish a solid foundation for the future implementation of bio-based coatings in a broader spectrum. At the same time, it will focus on developing business strategies for the industrial applications targeted by the project, with the specific goal of contributing to a safer European environment, stronger and more resilient industries, and new advanced materials.

The next PDEC at M24 will include the list of key exploitable results, their categorization, and foreseen exploitation routes and Intellectual Property Rights-IPR considerations, and will describe the value proposition, update on market analysis, patent analysis and risk assessment, as well as a review of the external environment analysis of the three industrial applications. Specific business plan strategies, internal environment analysis, final IPRs and marketing analysis will be developed for the final PDEC at M48.